

In-vitro Characterization and Silica-Nanoparticles for the Treatment of Liver Cancer Cells

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Abstract:

The development of nanocarriers for pharmaceutical applications is a challenging research field as they have to fulfil several requirements, such as suitable physicochemical properties, biocompatibility, loading capacity for therapeutic agents, high stability in the bloodstream, and specific delivery to the target cells. This task becomes even more difficult when trying to transport two different therapeutic agents simultaneously, as is required by most of the current therapeutic strategies. Mesoporous silica nanoparticles (MSN) fulfil most of these requirements, although they partially fail in the last two. However, these weaknesses can be circumvented if they are combined with another type of material such as polymers. In this context, the main goal of this research work was to develop MSN-based nanocarriers capable to co-transport drugs and nucleic acids and to specifically deliver them in liver cancer cells. To this end, we have prepared MSNs coated with lactobionic acid-based copolymers, as lactobionic acid has a high binding affinity to asialoglycoprotein receptors (ASGPR), which are overexpressed in liver cells. The designed hybrid MSN-based nanocarriers exhibited appropriate

physicochemical properties, high ASGPR specificity and high biological activity. These MSN-glycopolymer hybrid nanosystems showed a 280-fold higher transfection activity in liver cancer cells than bare MSN particles. Furthermore, we demonstrated the ability of these nanosystems to efficiently mediate a combined antitumor strategy involving HSV-TK/GCV suicide gene therapy and chemotherapy (epirubicin), in liver cancer cells. Overall, the data obtained showed the great potential of this MSN-based nanoplatform to be applied in combined therapeutic strategies for the treatment of liver cancer.

Keywords: Silica nanoparticles; Glycopolymer; Nanosystems; Cancer cells; Chemotherapy-gene therapy

1. Introduction

Liver cancer is the seventh most commonly diagnosed cancer worldwide and the third most common cause of cancer-related deaths, with hepatocellular carcinoma (HCC) accounting for 75 to 85 % of cancer cases. Over the last few years, immune checkpoint and multiple kinase inhibitors have been approved as treatment options for patients with advanced-stage HCC. [1] However, these therapeutic approaches face serious obstacles such as intratumoral heterogeneity, systemic toxicity and multi-drug resistance that limit their efficacy. New therapeutic strategies in cancer research have been explored and gene therapy has stood out with remarkable results. One of the best studied strategies is the herpes simplex virus thymidine kinase/ganciclovir (HSV-TK/GCV) strategy, [2] a suicide gene therapy approach based on the insertion of a gene encoding HSV-TK into tumor cells and subsequent administration of GCV. HSV-TK converts the non-toxic GCV into ganciclovir monophosphate, which in turn is converted by cellular kinases into ganciclovir triphosphate, which triggers cell death by DNA chain termination. [3] In addition, this suicide gene therapy leads to better therapeutic results, as the bystander effect involves the neighboring cancer cells and thus eliminates the need to introduce the therapeutic gene into all tumor cells. [4] Nevertheless, the clinical application of suicide gene therapy is still restricted by potential side effects that can be caused by different factors, such as the low specificity for cancer cells and the safety concerns involving the gene delivery vector, the transgene product, the prodrug, and the enzyme-prodrug combination, particularly when viral vectors are used. [5]

Fig.1. Schematic representation of the proposed anti-HCC strategy based on the combination of epirubicin and HSV-TK/GCV suicide gene therapy mediated by a hybrid glycopolymer/silica mesoporous nanosystem.

Recently, chemotherapy in combination with gene therapy has been shown to improve the therapeutic index against cancer compared to single agent strategies. This is needed an effective strategy to sensitize cancer cells to respond to drugs and to achieve an additive/synergistic antitumor effect with a lower chemotherapy dose and consequently with fewer side effects. [6] This approach potentially reduces drug resistance, while providing therapeutic benefits in cancer therapy, such as reducing tumor growth and metastatic potential, inhibiting mitotically active cells, reducing the cancer stem cell population and enhancing the antitumor immune response. [7] For a successful combined therapy strategy, however, it is necessary for both therapeutic agents to reach the target cells synchronously. Among the different types of nanoplatforms, mesoporous silica nanoparticles (MSNs) are considered an attractive approach for co-delivery of drugs and genes, mainly due to adjustable pore size, easy surface functionalization, morphology control, biocompatibility and high loading capacity for therapeutic agents. [8] Regarding the functionalization of MSNs, modifications with cationic polymers have been explored to better load and protect the nucleic acids. In the past, we have developed and evaluated different silica-polymer hybrid nanosystems for the co-transport of genetic material and a chemotherapeutic agent. Despite the promising results, the hybrid nanocarriers developed showed no specificity for the target cells. [9] To achieve specificity for cancer cells, targeting ligands can be attached to the surface of the nanocarriers, to enable specific binding to the desired receptors that are overexpressed on the surface of the target

tumor cells, but not on non-tumor cells. Cationic glycopolymers, synthetic polymers with carbohydrate groups, have attracted considerable attention due to their unique ability to mimic naturally occurring polysaccharides, promote specific recognition by carbohydrate-binding proteins (lectins) and increase the biocompatibility of gene delivery nanosystems. [10] In particular, nanocarriers based on glycopolymers of lactobionic acid, which are known for their biocompatibility and selective binding affinity with the asialoglycoprotein receptor (ASGPR), have rapidly emerged as a promising platform for HCC-specific gene delivery. Recently, we have developed a highly efficient and HCC-specific nanosystem for gene delivery based on poly(2-aminoethyl methacrylate hydrochloride) (PAMA) and poly(2-lactobionamidoethyl methacrylate) (PLAMA). [11] These polymethacrylate-based glycopolymers have been shown to be suitable for the preparation of nanocarriers for gene delivery with suitable physicochemical properties, high transfection efficiency, biocompatibility, and ASGPR specificity. [12] In this work, we proposed the development of a novel HCC-targeted silica-glycopolymer hybrid nanosystem, capable of mediating a dual chemotherapeutic and suicide gene therapy strategy to promote a potent antitumor effect on hepatocellular carcinoma cells. For this purpose, amine-modified mesoporous silica nanoparticles were prepared and coated with polymethacrylate-based glycopolymers. [13] Epirubicin was loaded into the pores of the mesoporous nanoparticles, while the DNA plasmid was complexed by electrostatic interaction with the cationic glycopolymers on the surface of the nanoparticles, ensuring protection of the genetic material and targeting to HCC cells. The effects of the structure of the glycopolymer (block or random) on the biological activity

and biocompatibility of the nanocarriers were investigated. [14] The best formulations of MSN-glycopolymer hybrid nanocarriers were subjected to comprehensive physicochemical characterization and evaluation of ASGPR specificity. The antitumor effect of a combined strategy involving the anticancer drug epirubicin and the HSV-TK/GCV suicide gene therapy strategy mediated by the novel co-delivery nanosystems, was investigated in HCC cells. To our knowledge, co-delivery of a combined chemotherapy and gene therapy strategy by hybrid polymethacrylate-based MSN-glycopolymer nanosystems has never been investigated. [15]

2. Materials and Methods

Synthesis of amino-functionalized mesoporous silica particles (MSNNH₂)

The synthesis of amine-functionalized tetrasulfide-based mesoporous silica nanoparticles (MSN-NH₂) was done according to our reported procedure. These particles were synthesized in two stages: (i) the

synthesis of nonmodified MSN (MSN-OH); (ii) the surface functionalization of these particles with APTES (MSN-NH₂). In a round bottom flask, 110 mL ultrapure water, 10 mL absolute ethanol, 900 μ L sodium hydroxide (2 M), 220 mg CTAB and 250 mg PF127 were added and set to reflux for 30 min at 80 °C while stirring at 500 rpm. After this time, the stirring speed was increased to 1,400 rpm and a mixture of TEOS/BTESPT at a molar ratio of 6.6/1 was added dropwise and left under reflux for 6 h. After synthesis, the particles were washed twice with ethanol. To remove the surfactants and thus induce the pores, the particles were sonicated and then left for 6 h at 80 °C in acidic ethanol (1:30 (v/v) HCl (36.5 %): absolute ethanol) under reflux with magnetic stirring at 1,500 rpm. They were then washed with ethanol (twice) and water (once). The resulting particles (MSN-OH) were then freeze-dried

Quantification of primary amines of MSN-NH₂

To quantify the amount of primary amine groups present on MSN-NH₂ particles, a fluorescamine-based assay was used based on a previously reported method. In brief, a suspension of MSN-NH₂ in NaOH (0.02 M) at 0.5 mg/mL was prepared. From this solution, 100 μ L was transferred to a cuvette and successively 2 mL of phosphate buffer (0.2 M, pH 8) and 1 mL of a fluorescamine solution (1 mM in acetone) were added. Fluorescence was measured at excitation and emission wavelengths of 366 nm and 480 nm, respectively, using a SpectraMax Gemini EM fluorimeter. The primary amine content of MSN-NH₂ was calculated using a standard curve with APTES.

Drug loading and release

For the drug loading, 5 mg of MSN-NH₂ were suspended in 1 mL of epirubicin (Epi) (2 mg/mL), sonicated with an ultrasound probe, and left stirring for 24 h protected from light on a roller mixer. After this time, the suspension was centrifuged (Eppendorf 5417R) to collect the loaded particles. Then, the loaded particles were washed (twice) with ultrapure water, freeze dried and stored at 4 °C until further use. The loading of Epi was determined by UV-Vis spectrophotometry at 480 nm using a SpectraMax Plus 384. For

this purpose, we used the three supernatants obtained from the centrifugation steps. [16] The mass of the drug loaded into the MSN was determined by calculating the difference between the total mass of the drug added to the MSN suspension and the mass of the drug present in the supernatants. The Loading Capacity (LC) and Entrapment Efficiency (EE) were calculated according to the formulas $LC (wt\%) = \frac{\text{mass of loaded drug}}{\text{mass of MSN}} \times 100$ and $EE (wt\%) = \frac{\text{mass of loaded drug}}{\text{mass of feeding drug}} \times 100$, respectively, where the mass of loaded drug is the mass of drug loaded in the MSN, mass of MSN is the mass of MSN in suspension and mass of feeding drug is the total mass of drug added to the MSN

suspension. The quantification of epirubicin in MSNEpi/ DNA/Gp-R was performed using the same method. The drug release studies of MSNEpi/DNA/Gp-R were performed in phosphate-buffered saline (PBS) solution (0.5 $\mu\text{g/mL}$), with or without 10 mM reduced L-glutathione (GSH), at pH 5 and 7.4. The nanosystem suspensions were maintained under constant agitation (160 rpm) at 37 °C. Calibration curves for Epi in PBS under the same experimental conditions were also prepared. At predefined time points ranging from 4 to 168 h, samples were collected and centrifuged at 14,000 rpm for 10 min using an Eppendorf Centrifuge 5415D. Finally, the released Epi was quantified by measuring UV-Vis absorbance at 480 nm using a SpectraMax Plus 384 spectrophotometer. [17]

Synthesis of glycopolymers

Glycopolymers were synthesized by activators regenerated by electron transfer atom transfer radical polymerization (ARGET-ATRP) using our reported procedure in the literature (Santo et al., 2019). The synthesis procedures of 2-lactobionamidoethyl methacrylate (LAMA), poly(2-aminoethyl methacrylate hydrochloride-*co*-2-lactobionamidoethyl methacrylate) (P(AMA-*co*-LAMA)), and poly(2-aminoethyl methacrylate hydrochloride)-*b*-poly(2-lactobionamidoethyl methacrylate) (PAMA-*b*-PLAMA) are described in detail in the supplementary material. [18]

Preparation of hybrid complexes composed of amine-functionalized mesoporous silica nanoparticles and glycopolymer

The hybrid nanosystem preparation comprises two stages. The first is based on electrostatic interactions between the positively charged amino-functionalized MSN (MSN-NH₂) and the negatively charged pDNA, the second on electrostatic interactions between the latter and the positively charged cationic glycopolymer. Polymer solutions (3 mg/mL) and MSN suspension (0.1 mg/mL) were prepared in ultrapure water with a pH of 3. To prepare the MSN/DNA nanosystems, a DNA solution (50 $\mu\text{g/mL}$) was added to previously sonicated MSN suspensions with different molar charge ratios (+/-, N/ P), mixed and allowed to stand for 15 min before seeding. For the hybrid nanosystems (MSN/DNA/Glycopolymer), the polymer solution was added after this time according to the desired molar charge ratios (+/-/+, N/P/N), mixed and allowed to stand for a further 15 min. MSN/ DNA without the polymeric layer, hereafter referred to as bare MSN, were used for comparison purposes. [19]

Transfection assays

For luminescence assays, 35×10^3 HepG2 cells per well were seeded in 48-well culture microplates and incubated for 48 h (5 % CO₂ at 37 °C). After this period, the cell culture medium was renovated by 400 μ L of fresh cell culture medium. Complexes were prepared as previously described using a plasmid DNA containing the luciferase gene (pLuc). They were added to the plate and incubated with the cells for 4 h. After that, the transfection medium was replaced with fresh cell culture medium, and the assay continued for a further 48 h. Afterwards, the cells were washed with PBS and lysed. The levels of luciferase protein expression in the lysates were measured by luminescence assay in a Synergy HT luminometer. [20] The protein content of the lysates was calculated by the DCTM Protein Assay reagent using bovine serum albumin as the protein standard. The results were expressed as the relative light unit (RLU) of luciferase per mg of total cell protein. To evaluate the transfection efficiency of the formulations, green fluorescent protein (GFP) expression was analyzed in the transfected cells by flow cytometry. Briefly, 1.4×10^5 HepG2 cells per well were seeded on 12-well plates and, after 48 h, hybrid complexes containing 4 μ g of pCMV.gfp were added to the cells. After 4 h of incubation (5 % CO₂ at 37 °C), the transfection medium was replaced with fresh cell culture medium and the cells were further incubated for 48 h. After that, the cells were washed and resuspended in PBS and immediately analyzed in a FACSCalibur flow cytometer (Becton Dickinson, NJ, USA). Live cells were gated by forward/side scattering from a total of 20,000 events and the data were analyzed using FlowJo software. For the competitive studies, the cell culture medium, containing 1 mg/mL of asialofetuin, was added to cells 30 min before the addition of nanocarriers and maintained during the 4 h of transfection. [21]

Cell viability

Cell viability under different experimental conditions was assessed by an Alamar Blue assay. After 48 h of transfection, the cells were incubated with DMEM-HG containing 10 % (V/V) of resazurin dye, prepared from a 10 mg/mL stock solution of resazurin. After 1 h of incubation, the absorbance of the medium was measured at 570 nm and 600 nm in a SPECTRAMax PLUS 384 spectrophotometer (Molecular Devices, USA). The cell viability was calculated according to the formula:

$$\text{Cell viability} = \frac{(A_{570} - A_{600}) \text{ of positive control}}{(A_{570} - A_{600}) \text{ of negative control}} \times 100$$

Where the positive control corresponds to cells without treatment (without particles and drug), while the negative control refers to the condition without cells and treatment. [22]

Physicochemical characterization of the particles and complexes

The particle size distribution and average hydrodynamic diameter were determined by Dynamic Light Scattering (DLS) on a Zetasizer Nano-ZS with Zetasizer 7.13 software. The zeta potential measurements were performed using a Zetasizer Nano-ZS coupled to laser Doppler electrophoresis and determined using a Smoluchovski model. N₂ adsorption–desorption isotherm analyses were conducted on Micromeritics

ASAP 2000 to measure the surface area, pore size, and pore volume of the nanoparticles. The Brunauer–Emmett–Teller (BET) specific surface area was calculated using the adsorption data at $P/P_0 = 0.05–0.32$. Pore diameter and volume were acquired from a desorption branch using the Barrett–Joyner–Halenda (BJH) method. The vibrational analysis of the MSN-OH and MSN-NH₂ samples was performed using Fourier Transform Infrared (FTIR) spectroscopy with attenuated total reflectance (ATR). The infrared spectra (4000–550 cm⁻¹) were recorded using a Perkin Elmer Frontier (FT-NIR/MIR) spectrometer, equipped with a FR-DTGS detector and a KBr beam splitter. The spectra were acquired with a resolution of 4.0 cm⁻¹ and 64 accumulations. A Perkin Elmer Universal Attenuated Total Reflectance (UATR) module with a diamond/ZnSe crystal was used, applying a constant force of 120 N in all measurements. Scanning Transmission Electron Microscopy coupled with Energy Dispersive X-ray Spectroscopy (STEM-EDS) was conducted to analyze the shape and topography of the MSN/DNA/Gp-R nanosystems and to confirm the presence of specific chemical elements. The nanosystems were dropped onto an HC400Cu100 grid (EM Resolutions) and left to dry overnight. The STEM analysis was performed using a Hitachi HD- 2700, type B STEM operating at 200 kV, equipped with a secondary electrons detector for highresolution imaging of surfaces and internal structures, allowing the obtention of Scanning Electron Microscopy (SEM) and Transmission Electron Microscopy (TEM) images. The EDS was carried out using a Fisons EA1108 CHNS-O Element Analyser with the furnace set at 900 °C and a helium flow rate of 120 mL.min⁻¹. The ability of nanocarriers to complex the DNA was analyzed by electrophoresis agarose gel (1 %, m/V) stained with GreenSafe Premium (NZYTech, PT). Electrophoretic separation was conducted at a constant voltage of 80 V for 40 min and the stained gels were observed using the imaging UV equipment StepOne® Detection System.

Antitumor activity

The best formulation (MSN/DNA/Gp-R at a 4/1/50 N/P/N ratio) was assessed to co-deliver Epi and a pDNA containing the HSV-TK gene (pTK), as a combined chemotherapy and HSV-TK/GCV suicide gene therapy strategy (MSNEpi/pTK), in HepG2 cells. The *in-vitro* antitumor effect was evaluated as

previously described. Various concentrations of epirubicin were tested (Fig. S5), and the concentration of 0.6 μM was selected as it was the highest one without substantially reducing cell viability, thus minimizing the probability of impacting the transgene expression. [23] The nanocarriers were prepared as described above and compared with nanosystems loaded with only one therapeutic agent (MSNEpi and MSN/pTK). Formulations were prepared with 181 ng of epirubicin (Epi) and/or 1 μg of pTK per well. For these studies, 3.5×10^3 HepG2 cells per well were seeded in 48-well culture plates, and 24 h after the different formulations were added to cells. Following 4 h of incubation, the medium was replaced by medium with or without GCV (100 μM). The cell viability was assessed at 72 h, 120 h and 168 h by the Alamar Blue assay. After each measurement, the medium, with or without GCV, was renewed. The cell death mechanisms involved in the different therapeutic approaches were evaluated by flow cytometry using

FITC-Annexin and PI probes in 12-well culture plates. After 120 h of incubation with MSNEpi/pTK/Gp-R and MSNEpi/pLuc/Gp-R, the cells were collected, washed and resuspended in 100 μL of PBS containing 0.05 μg of PI and 0.1 μg of FITC-annexin V. Cells were incubated (light-protected) for 5 min and then analyzed (10,000 events) in a FACSCalibur flow cytometer. The data were analyzed using FlowJo software. [24]

Statistical analysis

All the results correspond to mean \pm standard deviation, achieved from triplicates and are representative of at least three independent experiments. Data were analyzed by GraphPad Prism using one-way analysis of variance (ANOVA) followed by the Dunnett test or using two-way ANOVA followed by Dunnett or Sidak tests. For all tests, statistical significance was considered for p-values < 0.05 .

3. Results and Discussion

Synthesis and characterization of silica-glycopolymer hybrid nanoparticles

The preparation of silica-glycopolymer hybrid nanosystems involves two synthetic processes: the synthesis of amino-modified tetrasulfide based mesoporous silica nanoparticles and the synthesis of glycopolymers. The amino-modified tetrasulfide based mesoporous silica nanoparticles were synthesized by the modified Stober " method in two steps, according to our previously reported procedure for the synthesis of the unmodified MSNs (MSNOH) and their subsequent modification with the silica precursor 3-aminopropyltriethoxysilane (APTES) (MSN-NH₂). In this work, a combination of two precursors, tetraethyl orthosilicate (TEOS) and bis[3-(triethoxysilyl)propyl] tetrasulfide (BTESPT)

was used. The incorporation of the latter enables the synthesis of redox-responsive tetrasulfide based silica nanoparticles, as BTESPT contains tetrasulfide bonds that can be broken by reduction of glutathione (GSH), which is differently distributed in normal and malignant tissues (Huang et al., 2001). As surfactant, we used a combination of cetyltrimethylammonium bromide (CTAB) and Pluronic F127 to better control the pore size, as well as the size and polydispersity of the particles. In this combination, CTAB, as a cationic surfactant, is responsible for the formation of the pores, while Pluronic F127, as a non-ionic surfactant, is responsible for growth suppression and stabilization of the mesostructures. These surfactants were then removed by acidic ethanol extraction at high temperature yielding MSN-OH. As a result of the ionization of the silanol groups present in the surface, the silica nanoparticles usually have a negative charge. Since we intended to co-carry drug and genetic material, we modified MSN-OH with APTES to obtain MSNs with positively charged moieties (MSNNH₂), as this MSNs surface modification enables gene loading through electrostatic interactions with the negatively charged nucleic acids. Size and surface charge of the obtained particles (MSN-OH and MSNNH₂).

Fig.2. Infrared spectra of MSN-OH and MSN-NH₂.

Fig.3. Nitrogen adsorption–desorption isotherm and BJH pore size distribution plots (inset) of MSN-NH₂.

The average hydrodynamic diameters of the obtained nanoparticles were about 110 nm for MSN-OH and 151 nm for MSN-NH₂, with a narrow size distribution. Particle size is a crucial parameter to be considered in the development of suitable drug and gene delivery systems, as it affects the overall carrier's performance being a determining factor for the ability to penetrate the tissue and be internalized by the target cells. The size range between 30 and 200 nm is considered to be the most advantageous for drug and gene delivery systems (Sun et al., 2014). Both particles produced are in this size range. In addition, the large size of MSN-NH₂ compared to MSN-OH indicates the success of the functionalization process. Different values were observed with regard to the surface charge. While the unmodified particles showed a negative zeta potential (−32.7 mV) due to the ionization of the silanol groups, the amination strategy with APTES led to a shift of the zeta potential to a positive value (32 mV). Furthermore, these zeta potential values (higher than +30 mV and lower than - 30 mV) indicate that the nanoparticles are stable in suspension and have a low level of aggregation. The physicochemical characterization of MSN-NH₂

showed that the mesoporous silica nanoparticles were successfully modified due to the increase in size and the change to a strongly positive zeta potential. APTES functionalization was also confirmed by quantifying the primary amines grafted onto the MSNs using the fluorescamine method. The presence of a total of 147 μmol of primary amines per milligram of MSNNH₂ was detected. FTIR was used to determine the chemical composition of the MSNOH and MSN-NH₂ (Fig. 1). The FTIR spectra of MSN-OH and MSN-NH₂ are similar, primarily confirming the presence of silica. The prominent band at ~ 1070 cm⁻¹ and the shoulder at ~ 1220 cm⁻¹ are assigned to Si-O-Si stretching vibrations, while peaks

at $\sim 950\text{ cm}^{-1}$ and $\sim 800\text{ cm}^{-1}$ correspond to Si-O stretching vibrations. These results confirm the successful synthesis of the silica-based materials. The broad band at $\sim 3400\text{ cm}^{-1}$ is attributed to the vibrational mode of silanol (Si-OH) groups on the surface of the MSN-OH. For MSN-NH₂, the new peak at $\sim 1550\text{ cm}^{-1}$ is assigned to the N-H bending vibration. The band corresponding to the N-H stretching vibration at $\sim 3250\text{ cm}^{-1}$ overlaps with the silanol group band at $\sim 3400\text{ cm}^{-1}$. Additionally, the porosity and surface characteristics of the particles were evaluated by nitrogen adsorption-desorption isotherms (Fig. 2). Analysis according to the Barrett-Joyner-Halenda (BJH) method revealed an average pore diameter of 8.7 nm and a volume of 0.4822 cm³/g. As can be seen in Fig. 2, the pore diameter shows some heterogeneity, which could be due to the use of two different surfactants (CTAB and Pluronic F127). However, the pore size and pore volume are so large that a good loading capacity is achieved. In addition, the pore size falls in the range of mesopores (2–50 nm), so we can state that we have synthesized mesoporous silica nanoparticles. From Brunauer-Emmett-Teller (BET) method analysis we obtained a surface area of 221.5739 m²/g, which agrees with literature for MSN particles modified with APTES. Henceforth, these amino-functionalized MSN (MSN-NH₂) will be referred to as MSN. Concerning the synthesis of glycopolymers, we have synthesized several cationic copolymers based on lactobionic acid. Lactobionic acid is a natural ligand that targets the asialoglycoprotein receptor, which is abundant in hepatocytes. In addition, lactobionic acid has also been described as a biocompatible and biodegradable multifunctional galactosylated molecule (Alonso, 2018). For this purpose, a lactobionic acid derivative monomer (2-lactobionamidoethyl methacrylate – LAMA) was synthesized by reacting 2-aminoethyl methacrylate (AMA) with lactobionolactone. Then, two different copolymers based on AMA and LAMA monomers were synthesized by ARGET ATRP. The produced glycopolymers have similar compositions and molecular weights but different monomer distributions along the chain. It was synthesized a random copolymer PAMA-*co*-PLAMA (Gp-R) and a block copolymer PAMA-*b*-PLAMA (Gp-B). All synthesized structures, the 2-lactobionamidoethyl methacrylate monomer and the Gp-R and Gp-B glycopolymers, were physicochemically characterized by NMR spectroscopy and size exclusion chromatography techniques. Their chemical structures are in accordance with the literature. The composition and molecular weight parameters of the two synthesized glycopolymers, as well as of the reference polymer (PEG45-*b*-PAMA168). The main reasons to prepare our new hybrid nanosystems with these polymers are: (i)

protection of genetic material; (ii) prevention of premature drug leakage; and (iii) specificity towards target cells. In this context, our recent studies have shown that these glycopolymers are able to efficiently and specifically deliver pDNA to various liver cancer cells in the form of polyplexes (glycopolymer/pDNA complex structures). This shows that they are an ideal candidate for coating MSNs to obtain nanosystems capable of simultaneously delivering drugs and genetic material into liver cancer cells. We prepared different MSN/DNA/glycopolymer nanosystems, where the DNA corresponds to a DNA plasmid containing the luciferase gene, and evaluated gene expression via luminescence measurements (Fig. 3a) and toxicity of the complexes (Fig. 3b). The results presented in Fig. 3a show that naked MSNs are not effective in delivering plasmid DNA into HepG2 cells. This poor performance as gene delivery nanosystems can be explained by their low ability to condense the large DNA plasmid allowing its release and degradation before it enters the cells and reaches the nucleus. However, the addition of a glycopolymer layer significantly increased the transfection activity of the hybrid nanosystems. In addition, both random and block glycopolymers coated nanoparticles prepared with N/P/N ratios of 4/1/50 and 4/1/75, respectively, achieved 2.5-fold higher transfection activity than non-targeted PEGylated-based nanocarriers (MSN/ DNA/PP), our best polymer-silica hybrid formulation. Interestingly, achieving comparable transfection activity with block copolymer-coated nanosystems required a higher polymer amount than with the random copolymer. This difference can be attributed to the charge distribution in block copolymer, where charges are confined to a single polymer chain segment, while in random copolymer the positive charges are distributed throughout the entire polymer chain. This distribution of the positive charges throughout the polymer chain probably facilitates the interaction with DNA, allowing to obtain the best formulation of nanosystems with a lower amount of polymer than block copolymer-coated nanosystems. On the other hand, in this latter case, the increased polymer content in nanosystems, together with the accumulation of positive charges in a single polymer chain segment, most likely leads to the formation of areas in the nanocarriers with a high density of positive charges that establish strong interactions with the cell membranes, causing great membrane destabilization and, ultimately, increasing the cytotoxicity.

Fig.4. Transfection activity (a) and cytotoxicity (b) of MSN-based complexes in HepG2 cells. Cells were transfected using MSN/DNA, MSN/DNA/Gp-R, MSN/DNA/Gp-B or MSN/DNA/PP complexes prepared at different charge ratios (N/P or N/P/N). Asterisks (**** $p < 0.0001$, *** $p < 0.001$, ** $p < 0.01$, and * $p < 0.05$) cardinals (##### $p < 0.0001$ and ### $p < 0.001$) indicate values with statistical significance when compared to those obtained with hybrid nanosystems with the same amount of silica and glycopolymer and with MSN/DNA/PP nanocarriers, respectively.

These new hybrid MSN-glycopolymer nanosystems showed a 282-fold increase in transfection activity compared to bare MSN particles. This significant increase in transfection activity can be attributed, on one hand, to the enhanced protection of the DNA (as it is not exposed on the surface of the particle and is therefore less prone to degradation and premature release) and, on the other hand, to the role of this polymeric layer in facilitating the binding and internalization of nanosystems by HCC cells. These results emphasize the importance of MSN surface coating and the presence of a ligand. The cell viability studies performed in HepG2 cells showed that the cytotoxicity of the hybrid MSN-glycopolymer nanocarriers depends on the structure and amount of glycopolymer. In both the nanocarriers with random and block glycopolymer layers, cell viability decreased with increasing amount of cationic

glycopolymer. This can be explained by the multiple and strong interactions that can occur between cationic copolymers and the cytoplasmic membrane and/or intracellular organelles, leading to membranes destabilization of the membranes, which in turn impairs the metabolic activity of the cells. In addition, the structure (block or random structure) of the glycopolymers also played a decisive role in the cytotoxicity of the nanosystems. The results obtained show that nanocarriers produced with a layer of block glycopolymers exhibit higher cytotoxicity than those constituted by a random copolymer layer. This increase in cytotoxicity observed in nanosystems prepared with the cationic block glycopolymer is widely reported in the literature and is also consistent with our previous results obtained with PAMA-*b*-PLAMA-based polyplexes. In general, this can be explained by the configuration of block copolymers, which are less able to hide their cationic content than the corresponding random glycopolymers. Taking the results of biological activity and cytotoxicity in HepG2 cells together, the silica nanoparticles coated with the random glycopolymer layer at an N/P/N ratio of 4/1/50 exhibited a much better ratio between transfection activity and cytotoxicity than their block counterparts. Therefore, these Gp-R-based hybrid nanoparticles were selected for further studies.

Fig.5. Effect of the presence of free asialofetuin on biological activity (a) and cell viability (b) of MSN/DNA/Gp-R (N/P/N 4/1/50), MSN/DNA/PP (N/P/N 4/1/50) and MSN/DNA (N/P 4/1) in HepG2 cells. Asterisks (** $p < 0.01$) correspond to values that differ significantly from those obtained with the same formulations in the absence of asialofetuin.

Fig. 6. Topography (a), morphology (a-c) and elemental mapping (c) analyses for MSN/DNA/Gp-R nanosystems at 4/1/50 N/P/N ratio. Scale bars for SEM (a), TEM (b) and STEM-EDS (c) images are 100 nm. EDS maps of the MSN/DNA/Gp-R complexes (c): I) TEM image; II) silicon (red); III) sulphur (yellow); IV) nitrogen (light blue); V) phosphorous (purple); VI) oxygen (dark blue); VII) carbon (green); and VIII) overlay image of images I-VII. (For interpretation of the references to colour in this figure legend, the reader is referred to the web version of this article.)

Fig.7. Size (a), surface charge (b) and DNA complexation efficiency (c) of the MSN/DNA and MSN/DNA/Gp-R complexes prepared at different N/P or N/P/N charge ratios, respectively.

Asialoglycoprotein receptor-targeted nanocarriers

The asialoglycoprotein receptor (ASGPR), a target receptor overexpressed in liver tumor cells, has attracted considerable attention for the active targeting of HCC cells. This receptor binds specifically to galactose or *N*-acetylgalactosamine terminal residues of desialylated glycoproteins, with binding affinity increasing with the valence of the sugar residues, a phenomenon known as the cluster glycoside effect. To assess whether the developed hybrid MSN-glycopolymer nanoparticles are specifically recognized by the ASGPR on the surface of HepG2 cells, a competition test of transfection was performed in the presence of free asialofetuin, a natural ligand this receptor. The results presented in Fig. 4a show that the presence of free asialofetuin significantly reduced the transgene expression promoted by the MSN/DNA/Gp-R nanosystems, while it did not significantly alter the biological activity of the non-targeted MSN/DNA/PP nanocarriers. This reduction in transfection activity was not due to the toxicity of asialofetuin, as no significant changes in cell viability were observed after incubation with this natural ligand (Fig. 4b). To further confirm that the addition of a glycopolymer layer enables the specific recognition of nanosystems by the ASGPR of HepG2 cells, the effect of asialofetuin on transfection efficiency was also examined by flow cytometry. The data obtained confirmed that free asialofetuin binds to the ASGPR and impedes the internalization of MSN/DNA/Gp-R nanocarriers, resulting in a much lower number of GFP-expressing cells than in the case in the absence of asialofetuin. Overall, these results show that the developed hybrid MSN-glycopolymer nanosystems containing galactose moieties bind specifically to the ASGPR conferring cell specificity and increasing their transfection activity.

Physicochemical characterization of nanosystems

The physicochemical properties of nanocarriers, such as size, structure, surface charge and DNA condensation ability, are crucial parameters for a successful genetic material delivery into target cells. Therefore, the physicochemical characteristics of nanosystems were determined to evaluate their influence on transfection activity. The topography and morphology of the nanocarriers were examined using scanning electron microscopy (SEM) and transmission electron microscopy (TEM) (Fig. 5). SEM and TEM images revealed that the MSN/DNA/Gp-R complexes are uniform, spherical, and exhibit a homogeneous size distribution. Elemental mapping analyses showed a co-localization of key elements

from silica nanoparticles (silicon), DNA (phosphorous) and glycopolymer (carbon) confirming the layered nanosystem.

Fig.8. Release profiles of epirubicin from the MSNEpi/pTK/Gp-R nanosystem under biologically relevant conditions. Data are presented as the cumulative percentage of epirubicin released, expressed as the mean \pm standard deviation.

The DLS measurements shown in Fig. 5a indicate that the MSN/ DNA/Gp-R formulations are hybrid nanosized carriers (150–180 nm) and that their size was identical to that of MSN/DNA complexes, suggesting that the additional glycopolymer layer in the MSN/DNA/Gp-R nanosystems did not cause a significant increase in the size of the nanocarrier. This fact can probably be explained by the increased condensation of DNA by positive charges of the glycopolymer layer. Regarding the surface charge of the hybrid nanocarriers, a large difference in zeta potential values was observed for MSN/DNA complexes and MSN/DNA/Gp-R nanosystems. While the MSN/DNA complexes with the anionic phosphate groups of DNA on their surface exhibited a negative value of surface charge (- 15 mV), the MSN/DNA/ Gp-R formulations with the cationic charges originating from the glycopolymer layer showed a positive surface charge (~21–33 mV) (Fig. 6b). Moreover, the surface charge of these hybrid nanocarriers increased slightly with the increase of the cationic glycopolymer ratio, which probably explains the higher cytotoxicity observed for nanosystems with higher charge ratios (Fig. 3b). The ability of these nanocarriers to complex/condense DNA was investigated using a gel electrophoresis assay (Fig. 6c). The results show that nanosystems based only on silica nanoparticles (MSN/DNA) allow the migration of DNA through the gel matrix, suggesting that silica particles per se are not able to complex DNA efficiently, even at a high N/P charge ratio (8/1). However, the addition of a cationic

glycopolymer layer to the nanocarriers prevents DNA migration and this effect was observed even at the lower MSN/DNA/polymer (N/P/N) charge ratio tested. Cationic glycopolymers could interact with DNA via dual mechanism, namely electrostatic interactions (non-specific charge-charge interactions) and hydrogen bonding (directional dipole-dipole interactions) (Prevette et al., 2007), leading to strong complexation/condensation of the genetic material, which was not observed with the bare MSN/DNA nanocarriers. These results of DNA condensation together with those from zeta potential, which changed from negative (MSN/DNA) to positive (MSN/DNA/Gp-R), corroborated the data of the elemental mapping analyses that demonstrated the successful formation of the layered nanosystem.

Combined suicide gene therapy and chemotherapy strategy

To evaluate the potential of the developed targeted nanosystems for co-delivery of drug and genes, we investigate the antitumor activity resulting from the combination of the anticancer drug epirubicin (Epi) and HSV-TK/GCV suicide gene therapy mediated by the novel MSNEpi/pTK/Gp-R formulation, prepared at a 4/1/50 N/P/N charge ratio, in HepG2 cells. Epirubicin is an antineoplastic anthracycline molecule that inhibits the growth of cancer cells and causes programmed cell death by intercalating into DNA strands and inhibiting DNA synthesis. [25] However, this chemotherapeutic agent, which is frequently used in the treatment of HCC, leads to several adverse effects, in particular acute dose-limiting hematologic toxicity and cardiotoxicity, leading to treatment failure. Epirubicin was loaded into MSN (MSNEpi) using the solvent adsorption method. The MSNEpi displayed a loading capacity of 32 % and an entrapment efficiency of 81 %. To overcome the potential off-target effects and improve the therapeutic index, MSNEpi were complexed with 1 μ g pTK and coated with the random PAMA-co-PLAMA glycopolymer (MSNEpi/pTK/Gp-R). The drug release experiments of MSNEpi/pTK/Gp-R were conducted in PBS, with or without 10 mM GSH, at different pH values over a period of 7 days (Fig. 7). MSNEpi/pTK/Gp-R exhibited similar release profiles during the initial hours across all tested conditions. Differences became noticeable at longer time points (>72 h), with the most pronounced variation observed at 168 h. At this time, a higher release was detected under pH 5 in the presence of GSH, likely due to the cleavage of S-S bonds in MSN, facilitating epirubicin release. [26] However, overall release remained low (< 20 %) across all conditions, which can be attributed to the presence of two additional layers (DNA and polymer) that hinder rapid drug release. Furthermore, our previous drug release studies with MSNEpi alone demonstrated that epirubicin release was relatively low (~30–40 % after 7 days) compared to the nanosystem's antitumor effect, suggesting that intracellular conditions play a key role in promoting drug release. The antitumor effect mediated by the combination of

epirubicin and suicide gene therapy (MSNEpi/pTK/Gp-R + GCV) was compared with that obtained with the individual therapeutic approaches (free Epi, MSNEpi, and MSN/pTK + GCV) in HepG2 cells (Fig. 8). After 168 h of treatment with the combined therapeutic formulation we developed (MSNEpi/pTK/Gp-R + GCV), cell death of 84 % was achieved. [27] On the other hand, treatment of HCC cells with only the suicide gene therapy strategy or MSNEpi resulted in 55 % and 27 % cytotoxicity, respectively (Fig. 8a). As shown in Fig. 8a, no significant cytotoxicity was measured when cells were transfected without GCV treatment (MSN/ pTK). GCV was not toxic to non-transfected cells, either per se or in the presence of MSNEpi. Furthermore, these results demonstrated that our proposed combined chemotherapy and suicide gene therapy strategy mediated by this novel HCC-targeted hybrid nanocarrier exerts a potent antitumor effect with a higher therapeutic potential than the current therapeutic regimen with free Epi. [28]. To evaluate the mechanisms involved in the antitumor activity of the individual and combined therapeutic strategies, the extent of apoptosis and necrosis/late apoptosis was assessed by cell staining with FITC Annexin V and PI. As shown in Fig. 8b,c tumor cells treated with our proposed combined therapeutic strategy (MSNEpi/pTK/Gp-R + GCV) exhibited a higher percentage of non-viable apoptotic and/or necrotic cells after 120 h of incubation than cells treated with the individual strategies (free Epi, MSNEpi or MSN/pTK/Gp-R + GCV). Overall, these results demonstrated the ability of this novel HCC-targeted hybrid nanosystem to efficiently mediate a dual therapeutic strategy combining chemotherapy and suicide gene therapy with a potent antitumor effect. Although both normal hepatocytes and liver cancer cells exhibit higher expression of the asialoglycoprotein receptors (ASGPR), we are expecting a lower degree of cellular internalization of our nanosystems in non-cancerous liver cells compared to HCC cells, due to their lower metabolic activity. [29] Additionally, the chemotherapeutic agent used, epirubicin, disrupts DNA replication, a process that is much more critical for cancer cells than to non-cancerous cells, which are typically quiescent. Furthermore, in vivo applications, our nanosystems can take advantage of the enhanced permeability and retention (EPR) effect, which occurs in solid tumors, allowing nanosystems to accumulate much more in the tumor tissue than in healthy tissues. However, additional assays are required to clearly understand the clinical potential of this nanosystem.

Fig.9. Evaluation of the impact of the combined chemotherapy and suicide gene therapy strategy mediated by the targeted MSN-glycopolymers on the viability (a) and apoptosis induction (b and c) of HepG2 cells. HepG2 cells were treated with different antitumor therapeutic strategies: chemotherapy (Epi and MSNEpi), suicide gene therapy (MSN/pTK/Gp-R + GCV) and suicide gene therapy combined with chemotherapy (MSN@Epi/pTK/Gp-R + GCV). The concentration of the Epi used was 0.6 μ M. (a) The data are expressed as the percentage of cell viability with respect to untreated control cells (mean \pm SD). Asterisks $**p < 0.01$ and $*p < 0.05$ correspond to data from cells treated with each individual strategy (GCV, Epi, MSNEpi, MSN/pTK/Gp-R + GCV) or MSNEpi/pTK/Gp-R which significantly differ from those obtained with cells treated with the combined therapy (MSN@Epi/pTK/Gp-R + GCV). (b) Percentage of viable, early apoptotic, late apoptotic/necrotic and necrotic cells obtained from flow cytometry analysis, measured after 120 h of treatment. (c) Representative scatter plots of FITC-annexin V vs PI.

These include stability studies of the formulation in blood circulation, biodistribution analyses, and evaluation of its therapeutic activity in an HCC animal model. Anticipating potential challenges, we can optimize this formulation as needed. For instance, if the nanosystem exhibits a short blood circulation time, the surface charge of the particles could be neutralized by incorporating a small molecule of poly (ethylene glycol) into the glycopolymer chain. In addition, to overcome the challenges associated with intravenous administration, the therapeutic efficacy of the developed nanosystem can also be evaluated after intraarterial and intratumoral administration. Furthermore, we can enhance the targetability of this combined chemotherapy and suicide gene therapy strategy by delivering the non-toxic GCV using our previously developed MSN functionalized with a triantennary *N*-acetylgalactosamine (GalNAc) cluster. This targeting ligand also exhibits high affinity for the asialoglycoprotein receptor. [30]

4. Conclusion

In this research, we developed a silica-based platform capable of efficiently co-carry two different therapeutic agents - drug and nucleic acid – and to specifically deliver them to liver cancer cells. For this purpose, we coated MSN particles with lactobionic acid-based cationic copolymers with different composition distribution (random and block copolymers). We concluded that the random distribution of lactobionic acid units and positively charged units of the glycopolymer favored the biological activity of the novel nanosystem in liver cancer cells. This best formulation also showed good performance as a dual chemotherapy and suicide gene therapy mediator, with high antitumor activity in hepatocellular carcinoma cells. Overall, the developed MSN-glycopolymer nanocarrier is a major breakthrough in the still underdeveloped field of targeted nanosystems for combined therapies in the treatment of liver cancer. Furthermore, this new nanoplatform could be easily adapted to deliver new combined therapies for different diseases by using other polymers with specific ligands for the target cells.

Declaration of competing interest

The authors declare no conflict of interest, financial or otherwise.

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